

DESCRIPTION

ECOLOGICAL LIFE SYSTEM REGULATOR

5 1. Technical field

By utilizing Active (Effective) Microorganisms (EM) and various minerals, this invention provides;

10 A. the land that lost its agricultural / forestry land property, to regain its status of the agricultural/forestry land,

B. water and water resources (including wastewater) to be raised to a standart where all living beings can survive,

15 C. New natural habitats that will also affect the air quality index positively,

D. the continuity of ecological life system cycles,

20 and involves processes and methods related to a new biological and organic mixture called ESR-Y. Therefore it ensures to increase quality and cyclical continuity of soil, water and air, the three basic elements of a healthy ecological environment, which are included in the field of environmental technology.

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2. The current status of the patent is:

These two main components, mentioned in the present case, are used separately for this patent, which uses method / methods consisting of two main components, active (Effective) Microorganisms (EM) and various minerals. That is;

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A. Today Effective Microorganisms (EM) are widely applied worldwide for the purpose of soil rehabilitation, human health, treatment of waste water, organic fertilizer, making animal feed (silage) and its health, cleaning, elimination of bad smells, elimination of chemical hazardous wastes, etc.,.

In particular, it is the Japanese Professor Dr. Teruo Higa who has found the technique of keeping 82 organic microorganisms together in peaceful coexistence and holds the whole authority worldwide in his hands. The right to produce and sell microorganisms worldwide produced by this method belongs to him.

- B. As Leonardite mineral decreases the PH degree in soil, consists of humic and fulvic acid, and due to its organic substances and minerals, it is used as organic fertilizer instead of chemical fertilizer. Since there is no detailed study on this subject, the use of this mineral is based on non-scientific techniques. There are known methods for Leonardite mineral and its alternative uses and existing registration and authorization documents and productions on liquid Leonardite production. However; as a liquid soil conditioner; Costic Acid solution, which is used for the decomposition of Leonardit into its constituents, increases the Ph degree of the liquid Leonardite to exceed the normal value. That is, it is seen that the solution obtained is used in agricultural field with a minimum ph of 8-12 and above. It is clear that this method will not provide the desired benefits in agricultural land with increased pH values. This improper use will not diminish the use of external chemical fertilizers either, and will promote the use of chemical fertilizers continuously and dependently.
- C. In this case, the humus effect, which is one of the basic properties of organic fertilizer, will not be seen in the soil.

3. Scope of the Patent:

As already disclosed in this patent, there is no other method to separate all active and constituent substances that are harmful to vital elements such as soil, water and air and to transform them useful, and to complement the biological and organic elements by using the biological and organic mixture method / methods of Active Microorganisms (EM) and Leonardite minerals.

The present invention is a novel method of applying a new organic mixture which is particularly useful in the fields of environment, agricultural land, culture fishing,

aquarium sector, human health, animal health, plant health and prior art has been exceeded. According to the current situation, since the raw material is abundant, the production is very easy and cheap, it is suitable for industrialization.

5 **4. Description of the Patent:**

In this new method disclosed in this patent, the Leonardite mineral is put through microbiological processes, which are then broken down and separated into beneficial forms of useful acids, enzymes, organic substances ready to be absorbed by plants, minerals, various nutrients (fertilizers), so that the eco system is restored to its natural cycle and continuity.

If we explain this invention briefly with the current technical term "returning to the factory settings" regarding the mobile phones which are the most effective means of communication nowadays, nature is restored to its factory settings thanks to this new method disclosed in the patent. That is;

A biological (EM) and organic (Leonardite) mixture was found with this new method that supports the ecosystem cycle and / or ensures the re-eco system and complements the food chain. The resultant product / products and method / methods are briefly referred to as ESR-Y (EcoLifeSystemRegulator -Yiğit).

With this method, it has been found that humic acid and fulvic acid in the structure of Leonardite appears to have undeteriorate and low pH values, and as a result, lands that have become cancer or infertile and unproductive have been provided the opportunity to revive.

Also with this method, product / products which are suitable for the purpose of industrial use have been developed both as dense liquid and as granules. The product / products produced in both cases are applied to both soil and water and waste.

The solid product obtained as granule was enriched with other minerals and a new method was applied. These minerals are Klinoptilolite type Zeolite, Clay, Stream sand, Ceramic, Bims (also called Ponza stone), Leonardite which are minerals with high coal content.

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In this new method, new granular products were created using EM or Leonardite bacteria with the above mentioned minerals, instead of the known and so-called Bokasi ball method. This method provides the following benefits:

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A. These granules connects the chemical substances in the soil, that close to the leonardite type at the coal phase. In other words, heavy metals, chemicals, pesticides that cause pollution in the soil and increase pH are neutralized by this way. At the same time, due to the humic and fulvic acid released, the pH level of the soil starts to decrease.

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At the same time Fulvic acid transfers the moisture at the bottomn of the soil up so that it can be absorbed by plants and the moisture in the top layer of the soil keeps living microorganisms alive and functioning.

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B. Due to its porous structure, Clinoptilolite Zeolite absorbs heavy metals and moistures the soil by giving oxygen to the soil through ion exchange and converting it to useful acids.

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C. Thanks to Humic acid, fulvic acid and many other rich minerals, Leonardite on solid basis nourishes EM and / or Leonardite bacteria and soil.

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D. The BIMS mineral is lightweight, porous and water-retentive helping to balance the moisture in the soil and avoiding squeezing by loosening the soil.

E. The clay layers from Leonardite mines are also rich in Zeolite. At the same time, these clays are activated at high temperatures, creating an environment for microorganisms to grow and multiply.

- F. Because of the alluvial properties of the river sand, it provides natural nutrients to microorganisms.
- 5 G. Ceramic dust / fracture supports the formation of a permanent natural circle by providing the hold and breeding environment for useful bacteria.
- 10 H. The granules obtained by this method are designed in different ratios and dimensions (mm). That is, according to the current structure of the soil; cancerous soil, sterile soil, fatigued soil, low-yielding soil, and living soil, there are designs and methods at different rates.
- 15 I. According to the present structure of the soil and the products obtained by this method, first application is made at the rates, prepared for the purification processes of chemical and heavy metals, followed by the liquid method applications in order to enrich and revive the soil. Due to such reasons, different types of granule rates and liquid methods are applied.
- 20 J. By means of this method, the support needs and the usage rates given to the soil are continuously decreasing. This depends on environmental factors. (Drought, humidity, spraying, climatic conditions etc.)
- 25 K. No adverse effects such as excessive application, overdose are observed in this method. As it is a 100% natural method, it entrusts the eco cycle to nature. Intensive applications accelerate the soil cycle and allow for results in a short period of time.
- 30 L. Chemical cleaners such as chlorine, fluoride are factors that are reducing the effects during the application. In this case, only useful minerals, organic substances and useful acids are not affected. However, living microorganisms suffer from this. Accordingly, the natural cycle is adversely affected.

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M. Thanks to beneficial microorganisms, diseases on plants growing on the soil is greatly reduced.

5 N. In all tree and vegetable plant leaves, the liquid form can be easily applied by spraying.

O. The liquid and solid (granular) forms can be easily applied to waste and dirty water, streams, lakes and ponds factory wastewater and the effect will last.

10 P. The granule and liquid forms are also easily applied in commercial and ornamental fishing. It also removes the stress effect from the fish to prevent losses.

15 As seen from the existing Granule and Liquid Produced Leonardites by EkoLifeSystemRegulator-Y (ESR-Y) method/methods, in terms of production form and methods and application effects; the system, design and efficiency are completely different, it revives the ECO system, the effects are continuous, and by designing the soil and water very quickly, it connects heavy metals, chemical and
20 agricultural substances, then breaks them down, turns them into useful acid and organic materials, ensures a vital environment for plants and other living beings. When the EM method is applied directly to the pH value 9 and over soil and water, microorganisms can not find and disappear into the living space. In the direct application of the Leonardite mineral, there is a benefit that spreads to time and
25 process. This, makes it difficult to obtain the desired level of yield from the soil in a short time.

Thanks to these new method/methods, the high pH value of the soil; dependig on the usage rate, the usage range and climatic conditions, falls down gradually,
30 heavy metals in the soil bind to the chemical components, then they are broken down by living microorganisms and converted into beneficial organic substances and useful acids and enzymes in order to create a natural cycle in which living microorganisms can live and multiply. After this application, soil and water can start and continue its natural cycle in an increasing manner.

5. Detailed disclosure of the scope of the patent:

5 Unlike existing Leonardite solid and liquid applications that are being made in the world and in our country, these patented product / products are also classified as liquid and solid and have applications in fields of soil cultivation, fishery, ponds, streams, stock farming and factory wastes.

A. Liquid Applications:

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As a known method on the world, a solution is obtained by mixing with Leonardite mineral Costic Acid. It is a fact that 100% efficiency of Leonardite is reduced because this solution has high pH (hardness) values and Costic Acid deforms the properties of the main mineral.

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For this reason, the desired yield of liquid Leonardite can not be obtained, and the chemical fertilizer dependence is maintained. Furthermore, the formation of living microorganisms in the soil and in the water is also hampered by the high pH effect. The pH value of the solution with Costic Acid is 8 and above, while the humic acid value which is released should remain between 3 - 4.5 pH.

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In this patented method, from the EM (Effective Microorganisms) and the Leonardite mineral produced in laboratory environment, natural leonardite bacteria that is unique to their structure are multiplied and used.

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The Leonardite mineral is broken down, separated and transformed by these microorganisms. As a result of these processes; Humic Acid, Fulvic Acid, many useful minerals, useful acids, and enzymes are obtained in liquid basis. This liquid-based product has been directly applied to agricultural lands, so that ready-to-use nutrients have been obtained for plants and the soil cycle has been achieved faster .

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Unlike EM Technology, this method also allows plants to meet their fertilizer needs immediately and quickly due to their high mineral and nutrient content.

Unlike other methods; the beneficial bacterium formation and natural cycle process that must occur in the soil is accelerated by the living organic nutrients and microorganisms that we have created before.

Also this patented method has shortened the duration of effect in the EM method; furthermore plants have been nourished directly. Another additional support to EM is that the risk of affecting living microorganisms adversely by chemical and heavy metals in the soil has been removed from the soil thanks to the heavy metal and chemical bonding method in the soil.

B. Solid Applications:

The Leonardite solid applications known in the world and in our country use granular Leonardite, and the Zeolite mineral is used in greenhouses and limited use. In the far east, Bokashi balls are used. Bokashi balls are granule particles which provide continuous bacteria formation by applying to soil or water. Particles of granules called bokashi balls are made by mixing sand, ceramic, clay mixture with EM and drying them in the shade. In another method developed in this patent is that Leonardite, Leonardite mineral clay, carbonized Leonardite, Zeolite of clinoptilolite type and Bims mineral are used more intensively together with those mentioned above. The solid particles that we form from different rates of these minerals are soaked in EkoLifeSystemRegulator-Y (ESR-Y) liquid, which is the main product, and dried in the shade and made into a finished product.

Different types are obtained by mixing these minerals in different rates. These rates have maximum and shorter effect when adjusted according to the soil structure to be used.

Generally; the percentage of Leonardite is 50-60%. When used at 60%, Leonardite, which has reached the coalification phase in the revitalization of cancerized soils, acts like activated carbon and neutralizes the residues that we describe as heavy metals, chemicals and pesticides in the soil.

This application is an essential and Start application for diseased soil. It is followed by the application of the liquid method which accelerates the soil cycle.

The clay we use serves as a moisture holder and bacteria breeding ground. At the same time, it also has the ability to bind soluble harmful chemicals and convert beneficial acids and minerals by means of the hosting bacteria.

- 5 In case of mishap that may occur in rain and water, it releases the trapped moisture to the soil which provides the microorganisms to stay alive and continue their activities. Fulvic acid, released from Leonardite, also promotes the moisture deep in the soil to its surface.
- 10 Klinoptilolite type Zeolite is a useful type of Zeolite and is a mineral that is used in medicine and agriculture. The task of Zeolite here is to absorb the heavy metals, harmful toxins, chemicals, and to provide the soil with beneficial acids and oxygen through ion exchange in order to aerate the soil. Like clay, it is also a moisture-holding and binding agent. Zeolite is continuously kept active by beneficial
- 15 bacteria.

Stream sand will form an alluvial food chain for living microorganisms. Ceramic particles provide an environment in which bacteria are able to breed.

- 20 Our world has a wide range of minerals like Leonardite which will provide its own renewal. For example, it is reported that a Leonardit Mine has 120 million tons of reserves.

25 The aim of the method / methods disclosed in this patent is to make use of minerals that contain 100% organic nutrients and beneficial microorganisms, such as Leonardite etc in which no raw material shortage is experienced, and to generalize the use of organic agriculture all over the world instead of using chemical fertilizers.

- 30 Also; with this method, the heavy metals and chemicals components in the soil are bound and the ecosystem natural cycle is accelerated by increasing the functional effects of living microorganisms in the soil rapidly. Another positive effect is

preventing the formation of harmful bacteria in the soil, thus preventing soil rot and root damage in plants.

5 This method can also be easily applied in culture and ornamental fisheries. Visible positive effects have also been observed in problems such as abdominal distension, fungus (eye fungus), harmful bacteria formation, stress in fish. Chemical fertilizers are an addiction to plants. Because, unless chemical additives are provided to the barren or even cancerous soil, the plants can not grow by not getting nutrients and can not provide the desired yield.

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EkoLifeSystemRegulator-Y (ESR-Y) which is the raw material of the product / products obtained by the new method / methods included in this patent, rapidly transforms the nature into its original state, can be applied in four seasons, and is effective for a long time , and requires less use after each application.

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After applying EkoLifeSystemRegulator-Y (ESR-Y) in all agriculture and land territories, it is aimed to create high quality soil, high quality water, high quality and healthy herbal products and a healthy generation. In spite of expensive and limited applications of organic agriculture, it is aimed to convert every inch of rich soil into organic farming areas by making use of these mineral deposits with this new method.

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Each of the three main materials mentioned up to now EM, Leonardite and Leonardite bacteria obtained from it, and the main product, EkoLifeSystemRegulator-Y (ESR-Y) in which other minerals in different types and forms support the main product. In this way, it is possible to intervene quickly and efficiently to wide and different types of soil deposits.

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